

OSC Master Plan

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Logo

Open Science Community Amsterdam

Community Statement (Module 1)

Step 1 - Answer the following questions* :

- **Purpose**

- Why does the community exist?
.....
- What does the community hope to achieve?
.....

- **Member Identity**

- Who is the community for?
.....
- How will it affect the lives of members if they are part of this?
.....

- **Values**

- What is important to us as a community?
.....
- How do we want our members to treat each other?
.....

- **Success Definition**

- How does the community define success?
.....

- What does the ideal community look like?
.....

- **Brand**

- How does the community express itself?
.....
- How does the community communicate its identity to the world?
.....

*Questions based on [Community Canvas](#) (CC-BY-NC-SA). For more information, check out page 6 - 21 of the [Community Canvas Guidebook](#)

Step 2 - Write a Community Statement (max. 200-250 words) that describes your community, based on the answers you provided above.

Community Statement [who are we and what do we believe in?]

We, the Open Science Community Amsterdam (OSCA), are a collaborative initiative of the University of Amsterdam, the Vrije University, the University of Applied Sciences, the Amsterdam Medical Centre, and the Student Initiative for Open Science (SIOS).

We are a community dedicated to promoting openness, equity, integrity, and transparency in research. By joining OSCA, you'll be part of a network that fosters peer-to-peer learning and knowledge exchange among students and staff across Amsterdam's higher education institutions.

We aim to:

- Facilitate connections between individuals in a supportive, non-hierarchical setting.
- Host and support training, events, and discussions that focus on enhancing research quality, accessibility, and reach.
- Celebrate Open Science initiatives by our members and provide a platform to highlight their accomplishments
- Work closely with departments and academics to integrate Open Science practices into workflows across Amsterdam's academic institutions.

Join our community via our [website](#) and/or reach out via [email](#) to share your ideas, initiatives, events, etc. that advance our mission.

Being a member of OSCA not only enhances your own research and skills but also contributes to a larger goal of transforming scientific culture.

Step 3 - Discuss the Community Statement with 3-5 members of your OSC and revise your Community Statement accordingly.

Questions you could ask you community members:

- Do you identify with this statement?

- Is it missing anything crucial?
- Who does this statement need to have been vetted by in our community?

Community Engagement Plan (Module 2)

A. Target groups

Characteristic	Levels ¹	Ideal percentage of target group in your community (rough estimate, should add up to 100 per characteristic)	Why is this target group part of your community? What is in it for them?	How does this target group contribute to your community? What do they bring to the table? Think about the levels of the Mountain of Engagement (i.e., endorser, learner, participator, initiator, leader)
Career stage	Student	5-10%	Students learn about OS research practices to prepare for a research career, including applying for funding and enhancing the impact & quality of their research	This target group is not reached by all OSCA HEIs. There is opportunity to share know-across institutions to reach more students
	Early	50%		
	Mid	30%		
	Late	10-15%		
Institution/group	UvA	Equal representation	OSCA is a collective of 4	Every institution has it's

¹ Each row in this column can be considered a target group. It might be useful to number your target groups, so that you can use these numbers in the table below (Activities for community engagement).

	HvA	Equal representation	institutions	own challenges, achievements and resources in the joint effort for more open science
	VU	Equal representation		
	AUMC/VUMC	Equal representation		
	SIOS	Equal representation		
Experience with OS	Low			
	Medium			
	High			
Professional role (main focus)	Student			
	Researcher			

	Teachers			
	Research support			
	IT			
	Policymaking			
Categories of disciplines / methodologies	Humanities			
	Natural sciences			
	Social sciences			

B. Activities (list activities that you are already organising AND activities that you want to organise in the future)

Activity (e.g., workshops, meet-ups, hackathons, mentoring programs and of course your	Are you already organising this activity in your OSC?	What type of community interaction is part of this activity? (i.e., gifting, creating together, soliciting ideas, learning through use, networking	Target groups	Describe why this activity is relevant for this target group
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Launch Event!		common interest)		
OS Week	Yes	Networking, Training, Creating together	All (students, researchers, support staff, policy makers)	Provides a concentrated, high-energy moment to engage diverse audiences with OS topics through lectures, workshops, and networking
OSCAwards	Yes	Gifting, networking, celebrating, showcasing achievements	Researchers, teachers, support staff, students	Recognizes and amplifies OS contributions, building community spirit and highlighting good practice across disciplines
Knowledge exchange sessions across institutions	No	Networking, creating together, learning through use	All (students, researchers, support staff, policy makers)	Facilitates collaboration, peer-to-peer learning, problem-solving, ideas generation
OS practices inventory session	No	Generating insights, learning, networking	Teachers, researchers, research professionals	Helps identify current practices, gaps, and opportunities to tailor OS support and align efforts with real needs

C. Check: Do you provide activities (part B) for all your target groups (part A)? If not, try to think of ways to tackle this issue.

Plan to Attract and Onboard New Members (Module 3)

A. Community identity

Preferred associations	Associations to be avoided
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Egalitarian • Friendly • Helpful • State-of-the-art in research • Inclusive • Professional & goal-oriented 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Elitist • Science police • Cult • Dogmatic • Time & fund wasters

B. Communication strategy per target group

Note: you can copy-past the first two columns from your Community Engagement plan (Part A)

Characteristic (E.g. career stage; Faculty; OS knowledge)	Levels (E.g. early/mid/late career; OS newby/expert)	Value proposition (What do you have to offer? Why would they join your OSC?)	What is your key- message?	Channels to reach this group
Career stage	Student	Acquaintance with academic world	Become a member of the SIOS and get acquainted with good research practices with peers	SIOS

			through fun activities	
	ECR (PhD or PostDoc)	Contact with peers	Doing research can be a lonely job. Meet your peers and share experiences and good practices	Library onboarding program/Kenniscentrum managers/Landingsite
	Mid-career: Assistant or Assoc Prof	Enhance own visibility	Increase the impact of your research and your visibility as a researcher	IXA, open access lectures, spotlight interviews OS site
	Late career: Prof	Being an example	Inspire new generations for an open future	Personal/Thematic groups, like Methodologists network
Experience with OS	Low	Learning about OS	Take your first steps with support from a welcoming community	Workshops, onboarding sessions, OS Ambassadors
	Medium	Using OS to enhance research quality	Learn how OS practices increase rigour, collaboration, and visibility	Workshops, onboarding sessions, OS Ambassadors
	High	Inspiring others	Help shape a culture of	Workshops, onboarding

			openness—mentor, lead, and share your expertise	sessions, speaker opportunities
Professional role (main focus)	Student	Enhancing student research quality	Learn and apply OS principles to make your thesis more transparent and robust	SIOS, workshops
	Researcher	Increase transparency and impact	Increase trust, visibility, and reproducibility of your work	Workshops, thematic networks
	Teachers	Open educational resources/applying OS principles in your teaching	Enhance your teaching using open materials and tools	Workshops, thematic networks
	Research support	To better support researchers	Empower researchers by understanding and advocating OS practices	Workshops, Data Stewards network, library
	IT	Provide the tight infrastructure	Enable OS through FAIR-aligned tools, repositories, and platforms	SURF
	Policymaking	To extract guidelines for progressive policy	Translate OS principles into institutional policies	Policy roundtables, national OS initiatives

			and incentives	(e.g., NPOS)
Categories of disciplines / methodologies	Humanities	Existential crisis	Use OS to make your research more accessible and publicly engaged	Faculties and departments newsletters, thematic networks
	Natural sciences	Reproducibility crisis	Open protocols and FAIR data reduce irreproducibility and accelerate discovery	Faculties and departments newsletters, thematic networks
	Social sciences	Reproducibility crisis	Pre-registration, open data, and OS boost trust and credibility	Faculties and departments newsletters, thematic networks

C. Communication activities to reach (initial) members

Check: make sure to have campaigns for all relevant target groups (Part B)

Campaigns	Target Groups	Are you already doing this?
Open Science Week	All	YES
OSCAwards	Researchers, teachers, support staff, students	YES

Open Access Week	Researchers, teachers, support staff, students	NO
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D. Onboarding process for new members

Describe the onboarding procedure for new members in your OSC

- 4 onboarding meetings per year (one per trimester) with OSCA board, new and existing members
 - Members meet each other and the OSCA board
 - New members share their expectations, ideas and initiatives
 - New members get information about how OSCA works (events, calendar, etc.)
- All new members are signed up to the newsletter

Stakeholder Engagement Plan (Module 4)

LOCAL stakeholders (within your institute)					
Stakeholder	Goals and interests (overlapping, opposite)	What do you want to gain?	What do you have to offer?	Status of relation	Priority (low, medium, high)
Libraries (HvA, UVA, VU, UMC)	Overlapping in promoting OS	Sharing knowledge and resources	Network	Very good	High
RIOS (VU/VUMC)	Overlapping in promoting OS	Sharing knowledge and resources, network	Network and know-how, resources	Incipient	Medium
SIOS	Spread enthusiasm about OS among students	Future members	Network, skills, funding	Very good	High
Data Stewards	Mostly overlapping	Contact with researchers, needs of researchers	Free training, support, network, events	Good	HighBetter

NATIONAL stakeholders					
Stakeholder	Goals and interests (overlapping, opposite)	What do you want to gain?	What do you have to offer?	Status of relation	Priority (low, medium, high)
SURF	Overlapping	Better OS	Needs of researchers	Good	High

		infrastructure			
Other OSCs	Overlapping	Good ideas	Best practices	Good	Medium
DANS	Overlapping	Better data services	Needs of researchers and support staff	Good	High
NLRN	Overlapping	Best practices	Best practices	Good	High
OSCNL	Overlapping	Funding, networking, support, events, training	Outreach	Good	High
NRIN	Overlapping	Best practices, broadening perspective and scope	Best practices	Good	High
NWO	Partially overlapping	Funding	Projects	Good	High
Open Science NL	Overlapping	Funding	Projects	Good	High
Community of Practice for Open Naturally Occurring Data	Overlapping	Specialized knowledge	Specialized knowledge	Good	High
DCC's	Overlapping	Funding	Outreach, network	Good	High

INTERNATIONAL stakeholders					
Stakeholder	Goals and interests (overlapping, opposite)	What do you want to gain?	What do you have to offer?	Status of relation	Priority (low, medium, high)

COS	Overlapping	Training, infrastructure	Feedback and outreach	Good	Medium
INOSC	Overlapping	Representation, visibility,	Outreach, training	Good	High
QualaLab	Overlapping	Knowledge	Knowledge	No relation	Medium
FORRT	Overlapping	Best practices, training,	Outreach	Good	High

Monitoring Plan (Module 5)

Key Performance Indicator (KPI)	Target (when are you doing a good job?)	Information needed to monitor	How to monitor	Frequency of monitoring
Newsletter sign-ups	Growing	Sign up list	Yearly report	Monthly
OSCA events attendance	Growing	Attendance sheets	Yearly report	For each event
Submissions to OSCAwards	50 submissions	Submission forms	Yearly report	Yearly
Amount of members	Growing	Members of MS Teams and email list	Yearly report	Yearly
Representation of disciplines	Completeness	Extra info on member lists, topics of events, visitors of events	Yearly report	Yearly
Representation of OS topics	Completeness	Extra info on member lists, topics of events, visitors of events	Yearly report	Yearly
Representation of stakeholders	Completeness	Extra info on member lists, visitors of events	Yearly report	Yearly
Interactions between members	All interaction is good, but not always visible	Interaction in MS Teams, email, at events, etc	Yearly report	Yearly
Achievements in policy	OS documents created and signed by policy officers,	Documents about OS, policy reports about general	Contact with policy officers	Quarterly

	OS standards are achieved without policy being necessary	achievements in OS norms		
Member engagement	All interaction is good, but not always visible	Interaction in MS Teams, email, at events, etc	Collecting quotes and anecdotes (for example for the newsletter)	Monthly
Amount of events	According to plan for programming	Project administration	Project administration	Yearly report

Capacity Management (Module 5)

A. Available Resources

Personnel (hours)	0.25 FTE ambassador? UvA 0.1 FTE student assistant 1.0 FTE Community manager VU 1.0 FTE Community manager HvA
In-kind contributions (hours)	0.2 FTE (Raul) 0.2 FTE (Alexanda) Everybody 0.1 FTE
Budget (non-personnel) (EUR)	30.000 between 2024-2026 (6000 per institution)
Other (e.g. access to tools and facilities)	-

Required Resources

	KPI <i>Copy from your monitoring plan</i>	Activity/Deliverable <i>Copy from your plans of Module 2 - 5</i>	Deadline	Required resources (hour/budget/in-kind)
Community Engagement	Submission to OSCAwards	OSCAwards	Ongoing	5 hours per member Budget varies depending on attendance
	OSCA events attendance	Workshops, symposia etc	Ongoing	1 hour per member Budget varies depending on attendance and type of event
	Newsletter sign-ups	Newsletter	Ongoing	1 hour per member
Recruiting and Onboarding Members	New OSCA members	Double number of members	Next year	-
	More engaged new members	Through onboarding	Next year	1 hour per member
Stakeholder Engagement	Achievements in policy	Consultation meetings Presenting master plans to various departments	Ongoing	1 hour per member
	New collaborations for institutional partners	Consultation meetings	Ongoing	Variable
Monitoring	Creating an OS programme for your institution	Yearly report		

	TOTAL: at least 9 hours per member per month
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B. Increasing capacity

Project description	Funding opportunity

Governance Plan (Module 6)

A. Community Structure

Place here your community structure with the circles in your local OC. You can use [this template](#) to create the overview.

We are currently working on developing a members' lifecycle management

For each circle create a description including the aim of the circle and the responsibilities and any roles within the circle using the template below.

Events	
Aim	<i>Organize events</i>
Activities and Outputs	<i>OSCAwards, Trainings, Open Science Week, Discussions</i>
Responsibilities	<i>Planning, communication, promotion etc.</i>
Roles within this circle	<i>No fixed roles</i>
Relationship to other circles	<i>Relations: Funding makes events possible, onboa</i>
Resources needed	<i>Are there any (financial) resources this circle needs to function?</i>
Duration	<i>Is the circle permanent or temporary?</i>

Funding	
Aim	

Activities and Outputs	<i>Which activities belong to this circle? What outputs does this circle produce?</i>
Responsibilities	<i>What is this circle responsible for?</i>
Roles within this circle	<i>Describe the specific roles that exist within this circle?</i>
Relationship to other circles	<i>What is the connection to other circles?</i>
Resources needed	<i>Are there any (financial) resources this circle needs to function?</i>
Duration	<i>Is the circle permanent or temporary?</i>

Newsletter	
Aim	<i>Event</i>
Activities and Outputs	<i>Which activities belong to this circle? What outputs does this circle produce?</i>
Responsibilities	<i>What is this circle responsible for?</i>
Roles within this circle	<i>Describe the specific roles that exist within this circle?</i>
Relationship to other circles	<i>What is the connection to other circles?</i>
Resources needed	<i>Are there any (financial) resources this circle needs to function?</i>
Duration	<i>Is the circle permanent or temporary?</i>

Board coordination	
Aim	<i>Event</i>
Activities and Outputs	<i>Which activities belong to this circle? What outputs does this circle produce?</i>

Responsibilities	<i>What is this circle responsible for?</i>
Roles within this circle	<i>Describe the specific roles that exist within this circle?</i>
Relationship to other circles	<i>What is the connection to other circles?</i>
Resources needed	<i>Are there any (financial) resources this circle needs to function?</i>
Duration	<i>Is the circle permanent or temporary?</i>

Onboarding	
Aim	
Activities and Outputs	<i>Which activities belong to this circle? What outputs does this circle produce?</i>
Responsibilities	<i>What is this circle responsible for?</i>
Roles within this circle	<i>Describe the specific roles that exist within this circle?</i>
Relationship to other circles	<i>What is the connection to other circles?</i>
Resources needed	<i>Are there any (financial) resources this circle needs to function?</i>
Duration	<i>Is the circle permanent or temporary?</i>

B. Decision Making

**Think about the decision making structure you want to apply in your community.
How much freedom do individual circles and their members get to make decisions?
Where are decisions made that are larger than an individual circle?**

Who makes decisions?

Where are you on a spectrum between autocratic (leader decides) and participatory (group decides)?

How do you decide within a group (e.g. majority voting or more inclusive decision making) ?

Are there any perspectives (outside of your community) that you want to give a voice? What could be ways to include these perspectives?

Other OSCs (in NL and elsewhere)

INOSC

HEIs in Amsterdam

Amsterdam citizens

Sustainability Plan (Module 6)

A. Knowledge sustainability

There is a lot of valuable knowledge in your OSC through various documents and tools. Describe here how you want to document this information, so that new members can ease into their roles, without the loss of information.

Information	Related circle	Available where	Accessible to
OSCAwards organisation procedures	Events	OSCA Google folder	OSCA board
List of members & contact info	Onboarding	???	Alexandra
List of newsletter subscribers	Newsletters	???	Alexandra
Meeting notes	Coordination	OSCA Google folder	OSCA board
Resources related to past events	Events	OSCA Google folder	OSCA board
Funding application	Funding	OSCA Google folder	OSCA board

B. Financial sustainability

OSNL has provided all Dutch OSCs with funding for Community Managers for a period of three years. It is unlikely that additional funding will be provided after these three years by OSNL. So it is important to start thinking about how to obtain structural funding from your institution for the role of community manager. The good news is that the signatories of OSNL, which include UNL, have committed to provide structural funding for OSCs. We recommend taking a proactive role in this and remind people of this agreement to secure future funding.

Please describe here your plans and actions in order to secure funding from your institution

Note: this can also be included in your Stakeholder Engagement Plan

Actions	Deadline
Masterplan tailored to HvA Faculties	TBD
Meetings with VU library to discuss collaborative initiatives	On going
Student internships to support OSCA	September 2025

Subsidies for specific OS projects	On going
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